

EFFECTS OF BLADE COUNT RATIO IN FORCED RESPONSE ANALYSIS ON AERODYNAMIC FORCING OF A SUBSONIC AXIAL COMPRESSOR

Tetsuya Oshio
IHI Corporation
Tokyo, Japan

Mizuho Aotsuka
IHI Corporation
Tokyo, Japan

Atsushi Tateishi
IHI Corporation
Tokyo, Japan

Shinya Kusuda
IHI Corporation
Tokyo, Japan

ABSTRACT

This paper presents numerical investigations of the relation between unsteady aerodynamic forces due to rotor-stator interaction and blade count ratio (BCR). To this end, several unsteady RANS calculations are conducted with varying BCR. In all BCR configurations, blade was scaled according to its blade count to maintain the solidity ratio of each cascade, thus steady aerodynamic characteristics is maintained in each BCR. Firstly, it was confirmed that steady aerodynamic characteristics of both stator vane and rotor blade are not changed with BCR by comparison of time-averaged pressure on the blade. Secondly, it was shown that unsteady pressure fluctuation of rotor blade increases in specific BCR, and the increase occurs at around trailing edge especially. From the results of study about effect of stator-rotor axial gap and the speed of sound, the possibility of acoustic resonance in the axial gap or flow passage in cascade was denied, however it was found that the speed of sound also affects to the increase of unsteady pressure fluctuation. From considering of unsteady pressure field around the rotor, it was also found that the strength and mode number of Tyler-Sofrin mode which occurs by rotor-stator interaction on BCR and the speed of sound. Finally, phase speed ratio (PSR) was suggested as a new parameter which combine BCR and the speed of sound, and it was shown that PSR can organize the change of the amplitude of unsteady pressure fluctuation on blade by single parameter.

Keywords: Axial Compressor, CFD, Unsteady Aerodynamics, Blade Count Ratio, Rotor-Stator Interaction

NOMENCLATURE

BCR	blade count ratio
B	rotor blade count
$B_{original}$	rotor blade count of the original configuration
c	the speed of sound
C_p	pressure coefficient
f	blade passing frequency

N	rotor speed
m	mode number of Tyler-Sofrin mode
p	pressure
p_d	dynamic pressure
p_∞	pressure at free stream
PSR	phase speed ratio
SF	scale factor
θ	stagger angle of blade cascade
V	stator vane count

1. INTRODUCTION

In the design process of an axial compressor, blade forced vibration is one of the most important problems to be considered, since it causes high-cycle fatigue and threatens the structural integrity of the compressor. Since blades of recent aircraft gas turbine engines have become thinner and more flexible to meet the demands of performance improvement, it is difficult to avoid all of resonance points in the operating range. Therefore, existence of several resonance points in the operating range must be accepted. Either the resonance points are acceptable or not is depends on the magnitude of forced response, *i.e.*, either the stress due to forced response is lower than the fatigue limit or not. In such a situation, accurate blade forced response analysis is necessary to avoid blade failure, and to keep compressor performance.

Forced response analysis requires mode shape and unsteady pressure data on the blade surface to calculate exciting forces. Usually, the unsteady pressure on blades is obtained by CFD simulation. There are several ways to simulate unsteady flows in axial compressors by CFD, and the most basic way is to conduct multi-stage unsteady CFD simulation with sliding mesh technique. However, since full-annulus multi-stage unsteady CFD requires a large amount of computing resources, it is difficult to conduct full-scale forced response analysis in the design process.

To reduce the computational cost for forced response analysis, scaling method is often used. This method is to scale

adjacent blade rows to satisfy circumferential periodic condition with less blade counts. However, scaling of blade counts would change aerodynamic characteristic, and affects the result of the forced response analysis. To maintain the aerodynamic characteristics of the blade, blade shape is also scaled as to maintain solidity of the blade row. By using this blade scaling method, the change of steady aerodynamic characteristics would be negligible. However, it is known that the scaling of blade counts may change unsteady aerodynamic characteristics and mode excitability [1], and it is reported that this effect of blade scaling on forced response analysis is dominated by blade count ratio (BCR). There are several researches which investigate the relation between BCR and unsteady aerodynamics or mode excitability. Chen *et al.* found that the unsteady force acting on the blade changes non-monotonically with BCR, and the unsteady force increases at specific BCR [2]. Fruth *et al.* found that the effect of BCR on mode excitability depends on the mode shape [3]. However, the mechanism of changing unsteady aerodynamics and the details of changing mode excitability is still not clear. Therefore, a quantitative accuracy of forced response analysis with blade scaling method is still unknown, and correction of effect of BCR is still difficult.

The objective of this study is to clarify the effect of BCR in multi-stage unsteady CFD calculation. For this purpose, a number of simulations with different BCR condition have been conducted, and unsteady flow field are investigated to understand the mechanism of how BCR affects computed unsteady aerodynamics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Test cases

The compressor which is investigated in this study is Purdue 3 Stage (P3S) rig. This compressor is a subsonic 3.5 stage (including inlet guide vane) compressor for experimental use [4], and interaction between stator cascade of 1st stage and rotor cascade of 2nd stage was investigated in this study. Here, to reduce computational cost, 50% span cross section of this compressor has been extracted, and all simulations are conducted as a quasi-2D calculation.

The original blade counts of the compressor are 38 for stator vanes and 33 for rotor blades, and BCR is 0.868. BCR is described as equation 1, V and B are the blade counts for stator and rotor respectively.

$$BCR = B/V \quad (1)$$

In this study, BCR has been changed from 0.500 to 1.079 by varying rotor blade counts. All configurations are listed in Table 1. Rotor blades of each compressor are scaled so that solidity of blade cascade is kept constant, to maintain steady blade loadings. Scaling factor SF is determined by equation (2).

$$SF = B/B_{original} \quad (2)$$

Table 1 Configurations

Case	Stator	Rotor		BCR
	V	B	SF	
S38R19	38	19	1.737	0.500
S38R23		23	1.435	0.605
S38R24		24	1.375	0.632
S38R25		25	1.320	0.658
S38R26		26	1.269	0.684
S38R27		27	1.222	0.711
S38R33 (Original)		33	1.000	0.868
S38R37		37	0.892	0.974
S38R38		38	0.868	1.000
S38R41		41	0.805	1.079

Figure 1 Blade shape (arrow indicates rotation direction)

Here, it must be noted that the axial gaps between stator vanes and rotor blades are kept the same as original compressor in all configurations. Therefore, the axial gap per the stator chord length do not changes in all configurations to keep the axial gap per stator chord length. The 2D blade shapes for BCR=0.500, 0.868, and 1.079 are shown in Figure 1 as examples.

2.2 Numerical settings

In this study, the 3D Navier-Stokes solver UPACS which is developed by Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency has been used to obtain unsteady flow field. UPACS is a multi-block finite volume solver with implicit time marching method. More details of this solver are described in [5]. In the present calculation, the convective fluxes are calculated with a third order MUSCL scheme, and viscous fluxes calculated with a second order centered scheme. For turbulence modelling, Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model has been employed.

As aforementioned, all simulations were conducted as quasi-2D calculation. Computational domain and grid are shown in Figure 2. The number of grid points is 3 points for spanwise direction, and around 50 thousand points per a pitch for each blade row. Inlet section and outlet section were extended about 10 times of chord length of rotor blade to reduce the effect of

Figure 2 Computational domain and boundary conditions, computational grid

reflected pressure wave from inlet and outlet boundaries. Since the calculation is quasi-2D, slip wall condition is applied for both inner and outer boundaries. Non-slip adiabatic wall condition is applied for blade surface.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 BCR and steady aerodynamic characteristics

The change of steady aerodynamic characteristics of both stator vane and rotor blade with BCR are investigated in this section. Distributions of time-averaged pressure coefficient C_p on the stator vane and the rotor blade are shown in Figure 3. These figures show 6 cases for which $BCR = 0.6 \sim 0.7$ and original configuration. The horizontal axis of the graph indicates chordwise position which is normalized by chord length, and the

vertical axis indicates pressure coefficient C_p which is calculated as $C_p = (p - p_\infty)/p_d$. These distributions of C_p are in good agreement with each other in both of stator vane and rotor blade. This means that BCR does not affect to steady aerodynamic characteristics of the airfoil if all of blades were properly scaled.

When considering excitation of rotor blade by stator vane, wake of stator supposed to be a main source of pressure fluctuation. To confirm the change of strength of the wake, wake profile of stator is shown in Figure 4. The horizontal axis indicates circumferential position which is normalized by pitch, and the vertical axis indicates time-averaged total pressure which is normalized circumferential average. Wake of each cases are the same since geometry of the stator has not been changed. It is confirmed that the strength of wake of stator vane is independent from BCR.

Figure 3 Distribution of time-averaged pressure coefficient

Figure 4 Wake profile of stator vane (circumferential distribution of time-averaged total pressure at downstream of stator vane)

(a) Amplitude

(b) Amplitude (around LE)

(c) Phase

Figure 5 Distribution of 1st-harmonic component of unsteady pressure on the rotor blade

3.2 BCR and unsteady pressure on blade surface

The relation between BCR and unsteady blade loading is investigated in this section. In this paper, unsteady blade loading on the rotor blade which is induced by rotor-stator interaction will be discussed. Therefore, the frequency of unsteady phenomenon discussed in following part of this paper is a vane passing frequency.

To investigate the change of unsteady blade loading, distribution of unsteady pressure fluctuation on the blade surface due to rotor-stator interaction is considered. To quantify the unsteady pressure due to rotor-stator interaction, Fourier transform was applied to time-series static pressure data on the blade surface for single rotor revolution, and the 1st harmonic component of vane passing frequency was obtained.

Distribution of the amplitude and phase of unsteady pressure on blade surface are shown in Figure 5. The horizontal axis indicates chordwise position in both figures, and $x/C = 0.0$ indicates the leading edge (LE), positive and negative x/C indicate suction surface (SS) and pressure surface (PS) respectively. The vertical axis of Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b) indicate the amplitude of 1st harmonic component obtained by Fourier transformation of time-series pressure, and the vertical axis of Figure 5(c) indicates phase of the 1st harmonic component.

In Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b), a steep peak of pressure amplitude can be seen at LE for all BCRs. This peak is due to interaction with wake of stator vane. When rotor passes in the stator's wake, instantaneous incidence angle for rotor blade rapidly changes, and it leads to large variation of static pressure on blade surface at LE.

Focusing on locations other than LE, the amplitude changes drastically with BCR especially in region from mid-chord to TE of PS. The peak amplitude of S38R25 is over a half of the amplitude at LE, even though the amplitude in original configuration (S38R33) is almost zero at same region.

To investigate about the relation between amplitude of unsteady pressure and BCR, the peak amplitude in $|x/C| < 5\%$ and $|x/C| > 5\%$ are shown separately in Figure 6. C denotes chord length of rotor blade and these peak amplitudes are normalized by the peak amplitude of the original configuration (S38R33) respectively.

The peak amplitude in $|x/C| < 5\%$ (LE) varies about 35% from S38R33 at maximum, but these variations are much smaller than the variation in $|x/C| > 5\%$. On the other hand, the peak amplitude in $|x/C| > 5\%$ remarkably changes with BCR, and peak amplitude in S38R25 is over 4 times larger than original configuration (S38R33).

From these results, it is found that variation of the peak amplitude of unsteady pressure at LE is relatively small, and it is not varied with BCR. However, it is also found that the relation between BCR and peak amplitude in $|x/C| > 5\%$ is non-monotonic, and the peak amplitude is significantly increased around $BCR=0.6\sim 0.7$. As aforementioned, since stator vane is not modified in this study, the strength of the wake of stator vane is not varied in all cases. Therefore, an effect of the BCR on the peak amplitude at LE is relatively small, and it can be negligible in this study. On the other hand, the mechanism of the change of unsteady pressure in aft-chord is unclear, and it needs further investigation.

3.3 Observation of unsteady pressure field

In the previous section, it was shown that the amplitude of pressure fluctuation on blade surface other than LE drastically changes with BCR, and it leads to change of unsteady blade loading. To clarify the mechanism of this phenomena, unsteady pressure field around rotor cascade will be investigated.

The distribution of unsteady pressure is shown in Figure 7. Figure 7(a) shows the distribution in S38R25 which is the case that the peak amplitude on blade surface is the largest, and Figure 7(b) shows the distribution in S38R33 as a reference. These figures represent a snapshot of differential pressure from the time-averaged pressure at some point of time, and the value

Figure 6 Relation between BCR and normalized peak amplitude on the rotor blade

which is shown in figure is constructed by the 1st harmonic component of vane passing frequency of Fourier transformed unsteady pressure. There are five figures for each case, and these show time series variations, and time t indicates the time which is normalized by the period of single stator vane passing which is $1/38$ revolution in this study. It must be noted that these figures are seen from the reference frame of the rotor.

In these figures, pressure fluctuation occurs around blades in both S38R25 and S38R33. The magnitude of the variation of unsteady pressure in S38R25 is larger than in S38R33. This agrees with the trend of the peak amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface which is shown in the previous section. These pressure fluctuation forms stripe shape, and this stripe is moving circumferentially. These stripes are called Tyler-Sofrin mode (TSM) which is caused by rotor-stator interaction [6]. This mode is rotating around annulus, and rotating speed and direction of the mode depend on mode number. The mode number of TSM is obtained from following equation.

$$m = nB + kV = V(nBCR + k) \quad (3)$$

$$(n = \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, k = \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots)$$

The mode rotates in the same direction with rotor seen in the absolute frame when mode number m is positive. The unsteady pressure around blades shows different tendency with BCR, and it forms TSM. The mode number of TSM also depends on only BCR, since V is fixed in this study. Therefore, it is supposed that TSM has an important role on the change of unsteady pressure fluctuation on the blade surface.

In Figure 7, mode of $m = -13$ for S38R25, $m = -5$ for S38R33 appears in upstream of rotor cascade, and this mode is $B - V$ or $(n, k) = (1, -1)$ in both cases. The mode $(1, -1)$ which is generated between stator cascade and rotor cascade propagates acoustically in the passage, therefore mode $(1, -1)$ also appears downstream of the cascade in S38R33. However, mode $(1, -1)$ does not appear in S38R25. In the case of S38R25, mode $(2, -1)$ ($m = +12$) appears instead of mode $(1, -1)$ downstream of the rotor.

To investigate the difference in occurrence of TSM, the strength of TSM in each case is shown in Figure 8. The horizontal axis indicates BCR. In this study, the strength of TSM will be represented by the amplitude of Fourier transformed circumferential pressure distribution. The vertical axis of Figure 8 indicates the amplitude of m -th component of the Fourier transformation, and it is normalized by its 0th component value (which means averaged value) respectively. The amplitude is calculated at both upstream and downstream of the rotor, and these results are plotted in the figure respectively. According to Figure 8, it can be confirmed that mode $(1, -1)$ also exists in S38R25. Mode of $m = -1$ which is appeared Figure 7(a) is the superposition mode of mode $(1, -1)$ ($m = -13$) and mode $(2, -1)$ ($m = +12$).

Figure 7 Instantaneous snapshot of differential pressure at around the rotor (constructed with the 1st harmonic component of vane passing frequency Fourier transformation)

According to Figure 7, circumferential pressure fluctuation in S38R25 is clearly larger than the fluctuation in S38R33. Considering about the relation between the strength of TSM and BCR which is shown in Figure 8, it is found that the strength of TSM changes with BCR. According to Figure 8(a), mode $(1, -1)$ increases in $BCR = 0.6 \sim 0.7$ at both upstream and downstream. However, according to Figure 8(b), mode $(2, -1)$ appears in the same BCR range, but it appears at only downstream of the rotor. In addition to that, since the amplitude of mode $(2, -1)$ of other than $BCR = 0.6 \sim 0.7$ is almost zero, so that occurrence of mode $(2, -1)$ supposes to be a unique phenomenon under specific BCR. It must be noted that the trend of the strength of mode $(1, -1)$ and mode $(2, -1)$ are similar to the trend of the peak amplitude of unsteady pressure which is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 8 Relation between BCR and strength of TSM

From these results, it is confirmed that the change of the amplitude on blade surface pressure is related to the generation and acoustic propagation of TSM. Furthermore, considering the increase of amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface occurs at around particularly TE, it is supposed that occurrence of mode $(2, -1)$ which occurs only at downstream of the rotor is highly related to the change of amplitude.

3.4 Mechanism of increasing of blade loading

In previous section, it was shown that the amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface is increased around TE of PS in specific BCR, and the strength of TSM is also increased in same BCR region. From this result, there is a possibility that acoustic resonance occurs in the flow passage. Considering that all calculations are quasi-2D configuration, following two candidates are possible as type of acoustic resonance in flow passage.

- Acoustic resonance which occurs in axial gap between stator and rotor
- Acoustic resonance which occurs in flow passage of a cascade in chordwise or pitchwise direction.

In this section, possibilities of these acoustic resonance are examined.

First, acoustic resonance in axial direction at the gap between stator and rotor is considered. To investigate the occurrence of this type of acoustic resonance, calculations with different axial gaps between stator and rotor were conducted. In this study, axial gap is expanded by +10% of original gap in S38R25 and S38R33. The amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface is shown in Figure 9. Suffix “ax+” represents gap expanded configuration. The amplitude in S38R25_ax+ is slightly decreased since rotor-stator interaction is weakened by increasing axial gap, however amplitude around TE of PS is still large in comparison of S38R33. From this result, it is unlikely that the occurrence of an acoustic resonance in axial gap.

Next, acoustic resonance in flow passage in the cascade is considered. In this investigation, modifying of blade pitch or chord length should be avoid since these have a large effect to aerodynamic characteristics. Therefore, the speed of sound has been changed by changing inlet total temperature. In this study, inlet total temperature is changed about -13% and +13% from nominal condition. To investigate the effect of the speed of sound on the increase of unsteady pressure fluctuation, S38R24, S38R25, and S38R26 are chosen for test configuration. These modifications change the speed of sound +7% and -7% respectively. It must be noted that actual rotor speed was not modified to keep the vane passing frequency, therefore corrected rotor speed was also varied about -7% and +7% respectively. In this study, the mass flow rate is modified to maintain the relative flow angle at upstream of the rotor.

The results are shown in Figure 10. Suffix “SS+” denotes the case of increased speed of sound, and suffix “SS-” denotes the case of decreased speed of sound. The result shows that amplitude and phase of unsteady pressure is changed with the speed of sound even in case of the same BCR. The peak amplitude of S38R25 decreases in SS-. On the other hand, the peak amplitude of S38R24 increases in SS-, and it decreases in SS+. The peak amplitude of S38R26 does not change in SS-, but

it increases in SS+. From these results, it is found that the peak amplitude is changed by the speed of sound, however trends of the change are different in each case.

This trend of the peak amplitude is plotted in Figure 11. The horizontal axis indicates BCR, and the vertical axis indicates the peak amplitude on blade surface of $|x/C| > 5\%$. According to this figure, it is found that the BCR which takes large peak amplitude is shifted with the speed of sound. When the speed of sound is increased, the BCR of the largest peak amplitude condition moves toward higher. The scale of length such as a chord length and a pitchwise distance between blade and blade in blade cascade, becomes smaller when BCR is increased. If the reason of increasing the amplitude is acoustic resonance, the relation between scale of length and the speed of sound must meet the resonance condition, *i.e.*, the scale of length must be

Figure 9 Change of unsteady pressure in different axial gap

(a) Amplitude

(b) Phase

Figure 10 Amplitude of the 1st-harmonic unsteady pressure on the rotor blade (effect of the speed of sound)

proportional to the speed of sound under condition that the peak amplitude is large. However, in this case, the scale of length is in inverse proportion to the speed of sound under condition that the peak amplitude is large. From this result, it is not likely an acoustic resonance in flow passage of the cascade.

As a result of the investigation about acoustic resonance, it was found that acoustic resonance is not a reason of increasing of the peak amplitude and the strength of TSM. However, the fact that the speed of sound also affects to unsteady pressure field is clarified. To understand the change of unsteady pressure field with the speed of sound, distributions of unsteady pressure in case of changing the speed of sound under the same configuration S38R25 is shown in Figure 12. These figures are created in the same manner with Figure 7, and these are snapshots of the point in time when TSM at upstream of the rotor are in the same circumferential position.

In comparison among each case, occurrence of mode $(2, -1)$ at downstream of cascade is clearly different. Mode $(2, -1)$ occurs at downstream of the rotor in S38R25 and S38R25_SS+, however there is no mode $(2, -1)$ in S38R25_SS- unlike the other cases. According to Figure 11, the amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface also increases in S38R25 and S38R25_SS+. This means occurrence of mode $(2, -1)$ is related to the amplitude, and this is the same with the result which is shown in previous section.

As aforementioned, mode $(2, -1)$ occurs only when the amplitude of pressure fluctuation on blade surface increases. Furthermore, the mode occurs only at downstream of the rotor, and it depends on both BCR and the speed of sound. It is known that BCR directly affects mode number of TSM, however the relation between TSM and the speed of sound is unclear, and it is needed to investigate.

The effect of the speed of sound on TSM at downstream of the rotor is considered. The most likely effect of changing the speed of sound on TSM at downstream is the change of relative circumferential position from upstream to downstream, because it depends on the speed of acoustic propagation. The basic idea of this is described in Figure 13. In the figure, red

Figure 12 Effect of changing the speed of sound on unsteady pressure field (S38R25)

arrow indicates the speed of TSM rotation, and blue arrow indicates the circumferential speed of acoustic propagation through the cascade. The relative circumferential position of TSM from upstream to downstream is determined by the difference of red and blue arrow.

Now, the parameter which combines BCR and the speed of sound will be considered. First, circumferential speed of TSM shown as red arrow in Figure 13 is obtained by following equation.

$$V_{t,TSM} = \frac{2\pi Rf}{m} \quad (4)$$

Here, R is radius. Considering that mode number of TSM is calculated by equation (3), and acoustic frequency f is determined as $f = VN/60$, equation (4) is written as follows for mode $(1, -1)$.

$$V_{t,TSM} = \frac{2\pi RN/60}{(BCR-1)} \quad (5)$$

Which means circumferential speed of TSM depends on only BCR, if compressor geometry and rotor speed are the same. Next, the circumferential speed of acoustic propagation through the cascade shown as blue arrow in Figure 13 is obtained from the advection velocity of the flow field which is product of the speed of sound and relative Mach number, and the speed of sound as the following equation.

$$V_{t,acoustic} = (1 + M_{rel})c \sin \theta \quad (6)$$

Here, θ denotes stagger angle of the cascade, and M_{rel} is the flow relative Mach number. In this study, flow direction in the cascade is assumed to be parallel to chordwise direction of the rotor, so that circumferential component is obtained by using stagger angle θ . Finally, A new parameter phase speed ratio (PSR) is newly determined instead of BCR as follows.

$$PSR = \frac{V_{t,TSM}}{V_{t,acoustic}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 11 Effect of the speed of sound on the relation between BCR and peak amplitude ($|x/C| > 5\%$)

PSR is the ratio of the rotating speed of TSM and the speed of acoustic propagation in circumferential direction. The relation between PSR and the peak amplitude of unsteady pressure on rotor blade is shown in Figure 14. The horizontal axis indicates PSR, and the vertical axis indicates the peak amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface of $|x/C| > 5\%$. In calculation of PSR, the values at upstream of the rotor are used for the speed of sound and c and relative Mach number M_{rel} . By using PSR instead of BCR, both effect of BCR and effect of the speed of sound can be organized by single parameter.

The peak amplitude is increased at $PSR = 1.1 \sim 1.2$ in Figure 14. This result means that the peak amplitude is increased when rotating speed of TSM and circumferential component of speed of acoustic propagation is almost same. In other words, phase of unsteady fluctuation is always aligned in axial direction. Therefore, there is the chance to reveal the mechanism of increasing amplitude of unsteady pressure on blade surface by further investigation about the relation between TSM and acoustic propagation in the blade cascade.

Figure 13 Concept of rotation of TSM and acoustic propagation of TSM

Figure 14 Relation between PSR and peak amplitude of 1st-harmonic unsteady pressure on the rotor blade ($|x/C| > 5\%$)

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, several quasi-2D unsteady calculations with a different BCRs were performed to investigate the changes in the steady and unsteady flow fields. As a result, the following findings were obtained.

- As long as solidity of the cascade is kept constant, the time-averaged pressure on blade surface is not affected by BCR.
- The unsteady pressure on the blade surface caused by rotor-stator interaction varies nonlinearly with BCR and the speed of sound, and the unsteady pressure amplitude increases significantly for certain conditions. Unsteady pressure phase also changes significantly, which may have a non-negligible effect on the results of unsteady multi-stage CFD analysis.
- The strength of Tyler-Sofrin mode depends on both BCR and the speed of sound. The amplitude of this acoustic mode increases significantly for a specific condition, and in the same condition, mode (2, -1) occurs only at downstream of the rotor. This specific condition is the same as the condition that the peak amplitude on blade surface increases.
- PSR which is the ratio of rotating speed of TSM and circumferential component of speed of acoustic propagation can organize the condition for the amplitude of unsteady pressure to be large.

The present study shows that Tyler-Sofrin mode which generated by rotor-stator interaction has an important role on the pressure fluctuation in cascade. Considering that TSM is heavily depending on BCR, the scaling of blade count technique in multi-stage unsteady CFD calculation must be careful to use.

On the other hand, it was found that mode (2, -1) occurs only at downstream and it supposes to be related with the increase of pressure fluctuation on blade surface. Further investigation about this point is still needed to understand the mechanism of the increases of unsteady blade loading with BCR. If the change of unsteady pressure caused by BCR can be predicted properly, it may be useful to reduce the risk of harmful blade vibration in turbomachinery design.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to Guide 5 Consortium for providing geometry data of P3S axial compressor. The authors are also grateful to Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency for permitting for use the 3D Navier-Stokes solver UPACS in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Li, J., Kielb, R., 2015. "Effects of Blade Count Ratio on Aerodynamic Forcing and Excitability". Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2015, GT2015-43304, pp. 1-11.
- [2] Chen, T., Patel, K., Millington, P., 2012. "Combined Effects of Both Axial Gap and Blade Count Ratio on the Unsteady Forces of a Steam Turbine Stage". Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2012, GT2012-68874, pp. 1- 8.
- [3] Fruth, F., Vogt, D., Mårtensson, H., Mayorca, M. and Fransson, T., 2010. "Influence of the Blade Count Ratio on

Aerodynamic Forcing Part I: Highly loaded Transonic Compressor”. Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2010, GT2010-22756, pp. 1-13

[4] Murray, W., 2014. “Experimental Investigation of a Forced Response Condition in a Multistage Compressor. Open Access Theses”. Purdue University.

[5] Aotsuka, M., Tsuchiya, M., Horiguchi, Y., Nozaki, O. and Yamamoto, K., 2008. “Numerical Simulation of Transonic Fan Flutter with 3D N-S CFD”. Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2008, GT2008-50573, pp. 1-12.

[6] Tyler, J., Sofrin, T., 1961. “Axial Flow Compressor Noise Studies”. SAE Technical Paper, 620532, pp. 309-332.